

Decreasing Central Line-Associated Bloodstream Infections Acquired in the Home Setting Among Pediatric Oncology Patients

Diane Altounji, DNP, RN, CPHON --- Rachel McClanahan, DNP, RN, NCSN & Roxanne O'Brien, PhD, RN

Background

- Most children receiving cancer treatment require a central venous catheter (CVC)
- Caregivers are expected to care for and maintain the CVC at home
- Patients placed at risk for central line-associated bloodstream infections (CLABSI), increasing morbidity and mortality
- Leads to increased length of stay (Goudie et al., 2014)
- Cost of one CLABSI can reach \$70,000 (Wilson et al., 2014)

Purpose

The purpose of this Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) project was to decrease home-acquired CLABSI through improved hospital-based caregiver education regarding CVC care and infection prevention strategies.

Theoretical Framework

Albert Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory

Schematization of Triadic Reciprocal Determination (Bandura, 2012)

- Educators can modify these three determinants to enhance learning experiences
- Learners can make changes that will help improve their learning experience
- Influencing these factors can improve skill mastery and self-efficacy

Methods

- Conducted a literature review regarding the following topics:
 - CVC care
 - Best practices for CLABSI reduction
 - Caregiver teaching strategies
- Refined/standardized existing educational material used on inpatient oncology units
- Created a CVC skills competency checklist for caregivers
- Established two additional mandatory educational sessions for caregivers
- Created guide for nurses regarding required educational materials for caregivers

Project Intervention

Results

	Pre-intervention (Jan – June 2018)		Post-intervention (July – Dec 2018)		OR	95% CI	p-value
	Infections	New Diagnoses	Infections	New Diagnoses			
MBI	8	149	2	81	2.23	(0.43, 22.10)	0.50
LCBI	8	149	1	81	4.52	(0.59, 203.71)	0.17

- Classified CLABSI by category: laboratory-confirmed bloodstream infection (LCBI) or mucosal-barrier injury (MBI)
- Only caregivers who received the intervention were included in post-intervention sample
- Of the 109 newly diagnosed patients during the intervention, 74% (81) received at least one additional education session
- Nurses were able to complete 61% (66) of both additional sessions

Conclusions

- Patients in the pre-intervention group were 2.23 times more likely to develop MBI-LCBI and 4.52 times more likely to develop an LCBI-CLABSI
- Although statistical significance was not achieved, the intervention had a positive clinical impact
- CLABSI reduction led to prevention of morbidity/mortality, decreased avoidable inpatient days, and decreased healthcare costs
- Providing appropriate caregiver education is imperative to maintain favorable patient outcomes

Limitations

- Small sample size
- Inability to calculate outpatient catheter days for measurement of CLABSI rate
- Project leader was unable to identify every caregiver, therefore some did not receive the intervention

Recommendations

- Need for continued research regarding best practices for CLABSI reduction in the home setting
- Development of automatic trigger in electronic medical record for patients requiring intervention

For additional information, contact daltounji@csu.fullerton.edu